

Enhancing Resilience: Understanding the Impact of Flood Hazard and Vulnerability on Business Interruption and Losses

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Abstract

Flooding is becoming more likely and intense in a changing climate, which causes large economic damage. Households and firms are directly impacted by physical flood damage, but further ripple effects on society occur through business disruptions. This study adds to the literature on business interruption duration and losses after flooding by using post-disaster survey data from the 2021 Summer Floods in the Netherlands. Current empirical literature on flood impacts on firms is often unable to distinguish separate effects for flooded and non-flooded firms and does not incorporate flood severity and the influence of risk reduction measures. Here, we use multivariate regression models to determine depth-duration functions that describe the relationship between flood hazard characteristics and business interruption duration. This relationship can be used to calibrate flood damage models that capture indirect firm impacts. The predictions of business interruption after flooding allow for differentiation in business interruption between firms within a flooded area, reducing the reliance of these macroeconomic models on restrictive assumptions. A day of business interruption duration costs a firm on average 0.5% of their annual revenue; an effect that is stronger for firms with a weaker connection to their region. Flood damage mitigation (FDM) measures taken on the building level have the potential to reduce business interruption up to two weeks, indicating the need for policy to enhance FDM uptake among companies. Finally, quick damage compensation is found to reduce business interruption duration and thus revenue losses, calling for rapid and streamlined post-disaster insurance and government compensation.

Keywords: Floods, business interruption, propensity score matching, disaster impact, disaster recovery, adaptation

Acknowledgments

We would like to thank dr. Elco Koks for his valuable insights on the indirect firm impacts of flooding in the early stage of this research. This research was supported jointly by the Dutch Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management, Strategic Research of Deltares, and the REACHOUT project. The REACHOUT project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 101036599. ERC Grant Coastmove 888442 contributed to the participation of Jeroen Aerts.

Statements and declarations

The authors indicate that there is no potential conflict of interest.

1. Introduction

In a changing climate, it is likely that the intensity and frequency of natural disasters will increase (IPCC, 2021). Flooding is the costliest among natural disasters, causing over \$80 billion of economic losses in 2021 alone (Swiss Re, 2022). Floods directly impact households and companies through the destruction of their assets (Merz et al., 2010), which also results in disruptions on the housing market (Bin & Polasky, 2004). Further indirect ripple effects for society occur due to infrastructure destruction and interruption of business processes and financial markets (Hallegatte, 2015; Zhou et al., 2023). It is expected that business interruption losses exceed direct flood damage of companies, but only little research has been conducted on this topic (Chinh et al., 2016; Rose & Huyck, 2016). An improved understanding of the impact of floods on firms is essential for effective disaster risk management.

Business interruption is a major driver of post-disaster revenue losses (Hallegatte, 2008). Current literature that assesses the effect of flood-induced business interruption on firms is dominated by Input-Output (IO) and Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) models (Botzen et al., 2019). These models heavily rely on assumptions on business interruption duration and recovery paths, with little empirical evidence for this recovery process, which increases uncertainty in their estimations (Koks et al., 2016). Moreover, these indirect loss models often assume that business interruption duration is the same across all firms in the flooded area, regardless of the magnitude of direct flood impacts (Koks et al., 2016). However, large heterogeneity in business interruption has been observed in the few existing empirical studies (Thieken et al., 2016). Currently, studies that attempted to explain variation in business interruption only focused on pluvial flooding (Yang et al., 2016) or assessed variable importance, but did not quantify the exact impact of flooding on recovery time (Sultana et al., 2018).

Empirical evidence on the impacts of flooding on individual firms is thus relatively scarce (Lazzaroni & van Bergeijk, 2014; Zhou & Botzen, 2021). The available studies find mixed evidence. In the assessment of the firm's post-disaster capital, labor, and productivity, both Leiter et al. (2009) and Zhou & Botzen (2021) find that flooding stimulates capital and labor growth up to three years after flooding. The same studies find that the firm's added value decreases after a flood event, implying that productivity decreases. Noth and Rehbein (2019) find that flooding increases a firm's revenues within two years after flooding using German firm-level data. Disasters allow firms to invest in new capital, which may not have been possible prior to the flood event, due to the opportunity costs of capital (Noth & Rehbein, 2019). In contrast, Hu et al. (2019) and Pan and Qiu (2022) find negative impacts of flooding on firm performance.

These differences in economic losses and recovery paths seem to be mainly driven by the chosen time scale and defined spatial extent of the flooded area. With respect to the time scale, the studies that find positive impacts of flooding on firm performance all use a time frame of up to two or three years after flooding. The studies that find negative impacts use a time frame of up to one year after a flood has occurred. With respect to spatial extent, Leiter et al. (2009), Zhou & Botzen (2021), and Noth & Rehbein (2019) define a firm as flooded if a flood has occurred within a specific region, whereas Hu et al. (2019) and Pan and Qiu (2022) can identify flooding on the city-level. A similarity between all these studies is that they do not identify whether an individual firm is hit by flood water or not, let alone the severity of flooding. Consequently, the effect these studies find is the average impact of being located in a flooded region on a firm's activities, regardless of whether the firm experienced water intrusion or not. This average effect contains both the impact on flooded firms as well as spillovers to firms that did not experience direct flooding, and may even have benefitted, thus blurring the impact experienced by the inundated firms. A higher resolution of the flood extent allows for a clearer distinction between flooded and non-flooded properties, ignoring positive spillovers due to the substitution of production processes to nearby non-affected areas and increased demand for reconstruction, explaining the found negative effect. Additionally, these studies also cannot identify differences in flood magnitude and firm vulnerability between firms in the flooded area and thus assume that flood impacts are the same across all firms in the flooded area. However, flood hazard characteristics such as inundation depth and flow

velocity differ within a flooded region, resulting in heterogeneous impacts across firms during the same flood event (Thieken et al., 2016).

Studies that do identify whether an individual firm is flooded use survey data (Yang et al., 2016; Thieken et al., 2016; Wijayanti et al., 2017; Sultana et al., 2018). Wijayanti et al. (2017) exclusively focus on direct physical damage incurred by businesses, without examining the associated indirect losses. Yang et al. (2016) estimate business interruption losses using data from pluvial flooding in Japan and identify different business interruption losses at different flood hazard levels. Sultana et al. (2018) apply Machine Learning to identify the most important indicators that explain both business interruption and business interruption losses. It is found that longer business interruption is associated with higher revenue losses. However, they use absolute revenue losses as the outcome variable. Consequently, the predictive power of their models is relatively low, as absolute amounts of damage reduce comparability between different firms and economic sectors with very heterogeneous exposed economic activities and values to floods.

The main objective of this study is to explain the role of flooding on business interruption duration and business interruption losses using firm-level survey data from the Summer 2021 Floods in the Netherlands. This will be done by applying multivariate regression analyses to find the relationship between several detailed hazard and vulnerability indicators and business interruption duration. Next, firm-specific business interruption duration will be used as an explanatory variable to identify revenue losses in the wake of the flood event. A secondary goal is to identify the risk-reducing effect of flood damage mitigation (FDM) measures taken on the individual firm level. Generally, individual firms take fewer precautionary adaptation measures compared to households (Hudson et al., 2022). More information on the effectiveness of these measures may thus stimulate additional resilience for businesses. Up to our knowledge, no study has as of yet identified whether FDM measures have the potential to reduce business interruption duration. The estimation of the impact of FDM measures is prone to a selection bias, as individuals and firms that face higher flood risk are more likely to take FDM measures (Endendijk et al., 2023a). To overcome this bias, our study will apply propensity score matching (PSM), which is in line with other studies that analyzed the role of FDM measures on residential flood damage (Hudson et al., 2014; Sairam et al., 2019).

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the data used in this study, including the case study area, the survey and operationalization of the variables. This section also gives some descriptive statistics on firm impacts of flooding. In Section 3, the statistical methods are outlined. Section 4 presents the results on business interruption duration, the impact of FDM measures, and business interruption losses. Section 5 discusses the main findings in relation to the existing literature and gives pathways for future research. Section 6 concludes and gives policy recommendations.

2. Data

2.1. Case study area

In July 2021, parts of Germany, Belgium, and the Netherlands were affected by flooding due to extreme precipitation over a short period. This flood event resulted in fatalities, health problems, business interruption, and large economic damage. In the Netherlands, most economic damage occurred along the Meuse River, along with its tributaries the Geul, Geleenbeek, and Roer (Endendijk et al., 2023b). Return periods of peak discharges in these tributaries ranged between 1/100 and 1/1,000 years (de Jong & Asselman, 2021). This study focuses on the part of the Netherlands that was affected by this flood event, which is the province of Limburg in particular. It is estimated that approximately 600 companies and non-profit organizations and 2,500 households have experienced flood damage in this area (ENW, 2021). Dutch insurance companies have received around 10,000 damage claims from households and 1,250 from companies, where total damage has been estimated to range between €350 and €600 million (Dutch Association of Insurers, 2021a; ENW, 2021).

A share of the firms affected by the flood did not receive any compensation, as they were insured through stock exchange policies (Dutch Association of Insurers, 2021b). Flooding from smaller rivers and streams is typically not included in these stock exchange policies but is possible to insure through an additional insurance package. This resulted in a share of firms not being insured after the flood event of July 2021. Dutch insurers have been less strict in the compensation of households, which was not possible for firms due to the multiple international parties that bear a share of the risk in stock exchange policies (Dutch Association of Insurers, 2021b). The Dutch government supported some of these firms by partly compensating uninsured physical economic damage and revenue losses through the Calamities and Compensation Act (CCA) (Government of the Netherlands, 2022). As of yet, little is known about the direct and indirect flood losses experienced by firms and their determining factors, such as loss compensation.

2.2. Survey

The goal of the survey is to collect detailed information on individual firm's physical flood damages, business interruption duration, and revenue losses caused by flooding. Companies were also asked about flood characteristics near their location and to what extent they have taken FDM measures. The questionnaires were distributed by postal mail in three different waves to small and medium-sized companies. The first wave took place in December 2021 and targeted 857 firms located in the flooded area and areas in which an evacuation order was issued during the flood event. The flooded area has been determined by using helicopter images complemented by flood simulation models for the Meuse Rivers and its tributaries Geul, Roer, and Geleenbeek (ENW, 2021). The evacuation areas have been sampled to reach more affected firms, as there may have been some inaccuracies in the determined flood extent. The second wave started in February 2022, when a reminder has been sent to the firms that did not complete the questionnaire. The third wave sampled 606 firms in addition to the 857 that were already contacted for the survey. These firms were located in the same postal code area as households that experienced flood damage in the household survey of Endendijk et al. (2023b). This means that all firms in the sample are either flooded or a near-miss, which makes them relevant to include in this study. Also near-miss firms may experience indirect losses, as supply chains and accessibility for customers may have been disrupted (Merz et al., 2010).

These three waves eventually resulted in a total response of 215 companies (response rate of 15%). Approximately 40% of all firms are located near the Meuse River, 20% along the Geul River. For about a third of all companies, the geographical location is unknown, as respondents were given the option to refuse to share their addresses. The remainder of the respondents were located along the Geleenbeek or Roer. 83 (39%) of 215 respondents experienced water intrusion to their assets and 70 (33%) experienced physical flood damage. 60% of all surveyed firms experienced business interruption, which indicates that business interruption even occurs when the firm's properties have not been flooded. This is confirmed by Figure 1, which gives insight into the distribution of the absolute direct damage and revenue losses after flooding. More firms experienced revenue losses than direct damage, where revenue losses are in most cases larger than physical damage to properties. Flood impacts on firms strongly differ per economic sector (Sieg et al., 2017; Koks et al., 2019). Figure 2 shows that there is a large variety of included firms, where most surveyed firms are active in the hospitality sector (hotels, restaurants, campsites).

Figure 1

Distribution of the direct physical damage (blue) and revenue losses (orange) of the firms in the sample.

2.3. Variables and operationalization

Table 1 gives an overview of the variables included in this study. The two main dependent variables of interest are business interruption in days and revenue losses after the flood event in July 2021. Both revenue losses and business interruption duration are reported by the firm. However, since not all firms knew their revenue or business interruption, some observations are missing in the regression. There is a large heterogeneity between firm sizes when using absolute values for revenue losses (Sultana et al., 2018). To allow for comparison between different firm sizes, we normalized revenue losses by relating these to the annual revenue of 2019 and define this as the revenue loss ratio. We decided to relate revenue losses to the 2019 annual revenue rather than the 2020 annual revenue, as the COVID-19 pandemic resulted in strong revenue shocks within most economic sectors (Fahlenbrach et al., 2021). As the July 2021 flood occurred in a period with less strict COVID-19 regulations in the Netherlands, we believe that relating revenue losses to 2019 annual revenue from before the pandemic will give a more realistic representation of firm sizes compared to 2020 revenues, during a period with the most strict lockdowns.

The mean business interruption for flooded firms in our sample is fifteen days and two days for non-flooded firms. Figure 2 differentiates both business interruption and revenue losses for economic sectors. It becomes apparent that both outcome variables follow a right-tailed distribution with also large differences within economic sectors. Looking at the median business interruption, the hospitality and public sector were the longest out of business. A potential explanation for this is that the hospitality and public sectors are both labor-intensive and location-bound. In the first few weeks after a flood event, firms may temporarily face employment shortages, as employees may be occupied elsewhere in the recovery after a flood event (Sultana et al., 2018). These employees may need to clean up and repair their own homes or help in their social network after the flood event. Additionally, cleaning up the firm's assets takes longer as well, as these firms only open when the entire property is fully cleaned. Mean business interruption for the health and manufacturing sectors shows strong deviations from the median. From the right section of Table 1 can be observed that sectors with larger median business interruption also face larger median revenue losses. The service sector faces the lowest business interruption, as operations are often not bound to a physical location.

Figure 2

Business interruption (left) and revenue losses (right) for different economic sectors. The 25th percentile, median and 75th percentile are shown in blue, mean in red.

We describe flood impacts on the firm level using the risk framework defined by Kron (2005), who defines risk as a function of hazard, exposure, and vulnerability. All variables used to explain both business interruption duration and revenue losses can be related to one of these categories; where hazard describes the severity of the flood event, exposure the value at risk, and vulnerability the firm's susceptibility to flooding (Kron, 2005). Besides the two dependent variables in this study, Table 1 also describes all explanatory variables related to the risk framework. The hazard components included are inundation depth at the ground floor of the firm's main property, flow velocity, and floodwater contamination. The variable inundation depth is often used through depth-damage curves in physical flood risk models that form the basis for indirect flood loss assessments (Koks et al., 2016).

The variable *access difficulty* has been included as a proxy for supply chain disruptions. Revenues may be harmed when a firm is difficult to access for customers, suppliers, or employees, even though the firm is operational already (Tierney, 1997). Figure 3 gives an overview of the days the firm was difficult to reach. More than half of the firms that were not inundated remained accessible at all times after the flood event. Only for a small fraction, this difficulty to access lasted longer than a week. The difficulty to access the firm is more evenly distributed for the flooded group. Where a bit over 20% of the inundated firms were difficult to access for more than a week after the flood event.

Figure 3

Relative frequency of the number of days of the firm being difficult to access for customers, suppliers, or employees after the flood event, separated by the firm being inundated (blue) or not (orange). The number of observations given on top of the bars.

With respect to exposure, we control for firm size in the regressions by using the number of employees prior to the flood event. Next, firm impacts greatly differ between economic sectors, also driven by how capital-intensive these sectors are (Leiter et al., 2009). For this reason, we include sector fixed-effects in the analysis. The final exposure indicator included is whether the firm is located along the Geul River or not. Figure 8 in Appendix I gives a geographical distribution of business interruption of the sample. Although the sample per postal code area is relatively small, the figure indicates that average business interruption is the largest along the Geul River. For this reason, we control for the firm's presence along the Geul River, as a proxy for larger disruptions in infrastructure and supply chains in this area. Moreover, Endendijk et al. (2023b) show that household losses are also concentrated along this river.

To capture individual firm preparedness and vulnerability, we include FDM measures and building age as indicators that affect vulnerability through physical damage. In line with Endendijk et al. (2023a), we distinguish between two different FDM category distinctions.¹ First, wet-proofing and dry-proofing refer to the goal of the FDM measure. Wet-proofing is aimed at reducing the impact of the water, once it has already intruded the building (e.g., building with waterproof materials, elevating electrical appliances). Dry-proofing refers to measures targeted at keeping the water outside of the building (e.g., placing barriers, or elevating the building). De Ruig et al. (2022) indicate that dry-proofing is generally effective with shallow inundation depths. Another distinction is made between emergency FDM and structural FDM. Emergency FDM is taken in advance of a flood event, often after an early warning is given (e.g., placing sandbags, moving household contents to higher floors), while structural FDM is applied in advance of a potential flood event (e.g., building with waterproof materials, elevating the building). Note that the distinctions between wet- and dry-proofing on the one side and emergency FDM and structural FDM are not mutually exclusive (e.g., sandbags are both a dry-proofing and emergency FDM measure). The distinctions are included this way to allow for more generalization to both modelling and policy contexts (Endendijk et al., 2023a). The variable supply dependency has been added as a vulnerability indicator because firms are more resilient to supply chain disruptions if they can operate longer without receiving additional stocks (Koks et al., 2016). The variable region connection describes the firm's connection to the region, which may alter the impacts of business interruption on revenue losses.

¹ For a full overview of all included individual FDM measures within each category group, see Endendijk et al. (2023a).

Table 1
Overview of the included variables in this study (N=223).

Variable	Description	Mean
<i>Firm impacts</i>		
Business interruption	The number of days the firm is unable to operate due to flooding.	6.69 (14.89)
Revenue loss ratio	The ratio between the firm's revenue losses due to flooding and the 2019 annual revenue.	0.08 (0.16)
<i>Hazard</i>		
Inundation depth	Inundation depth at the ground floor of the firm's main property in centimeters.	28.86 (51.58)
Flow velocity	Ordinal variable describing flow velocity (1=average man could easily stand up, 2=average man could barely stand, 3=average man would have been swept away).	1.84 (0.91)
Contamination	Dummy variable with the value 1 if the flood water near the firm's location has been contaminated by either oil, chemicals, sewage materials, or other waste, and the value 0 otherwise.	0.26 (0.44)
Access difficulty	Days of the firm being difficult to access for either customers, suppliers, or employees.	2.64 (3.39)
<i>Exposure</i>		
Employees	The absolute number of employees prior to the flood event of July 2021.	18.85 (42.64)
Geul river	Dummy variable with the value 1 if the firm is located near the river Geul and value 0 otherwise.	0.18 (0.38)
Sector	Dummy variable with the value 1 if the firm is operating within the respective economic sector from Table 1 and value 0 otherwise.	See Figure 2
<i>Vulnerability</i>		
Building age	Years since the firm's main building has been built.	82.36 (88.31)
Supply dependency	Days the firm can operate without stock inflow.	34.78 (29.30)
Region connection	Dummy variable with the value 1 if at least 50% of the firm's customers or suppliers are located within a 10 km radius around the firm and value 0 otherwise.	0.22 (0.41)
Received compensation (%)	The percentage of compensation the firm received at the time of the survey (6-8 months after flooding) related to total expected compensation.	92.91 (23.18)
<i>FDM</i>		
Dry-proofing	Dummy variable with the value 1 if the firm has taken dry-proofing measures aimed at keeping the water out of the building before the flood event and the value 0 otherwise.	0.31 (0.47)
Wet-proofing	Dummy variable with the value 1 if the firm has taken wet-proofing measures aimed at reducing flood damage once the water enters the building before the flood event and value 0 otherwise.	0.49 (0.50)
Structural FDM	Dummy variable with the value 1 if the firm has taken structural FDM measures as precautionary measures before a future flood event and the value 0 otherwise.	0.34 (0.47)
Emergency FDM	Dummy variable with the value 1 if the firm has taken emergency FDM measures shortly before the flood event and value 0 otherwise.	0.49 (0.50)

Note: Standard deviations in parentheses

The restoration of direct flood damage prolongs business interruption (Ma et al., 2021) and insurance compensation supports post-disaster recovery (Kreibich et al., 2007). For firm impacts, the percentage of received compensation related to total expected compensation has been included, which reflects a received compensation fraction at the time of the survey. Figure 4 gives an overview of the progress of compensation six to eight months after the 2021 Summer Floods. The amount of still expected compensation corresponds to the firms that are waiting for insurance or government payments. However, it may be possible that respondents were overestimating their compensation, where in reality these firms are not eligible for this compensation. As a relatively large part of the firms was not insured

against flood damage, the Calamities Compensation Act² (CCA) is the largest form of compensation in our sample.

The ratios between still expected and total compensation are lower compared to the mean of the *received compensation* variable in Table 1, as there is also a large share that did not experience physical flood damage, and thus does not expect any compensation. It stands out that the major share of compensation from the inventory insurance has already been paid out six to eight months after the flood. The building and consequential loss insurance are slower in their compensation, possibly due to that these claims are more difficult to assess. The two public compensation schemes (the CCA and Disaster Fund³) have both paid out more than half of the total expected compensation by firms. Overall, firms expect that 61.2% of their total losses (i.e., physical damage and revenue losses) after the flood event will be compensated by either insurance or public compensation schemes, which would be substantially lower if not for the public compensation schemes that compensate damage for uninsured firms. This indicates that around 40% of all economic losses experienced by companies were not compensated after the flood event; a number that is similar to the findings for household loss compensation, where also 40% of all losses were not compensated (Endendijk et al., 2023b). However, households received a larger share of their compensation from their home or contents insurance, whereas firms relied more on the government's leniency for compensation of damages after the flood.

Figure 4

Total received and still expected compensation from insurance policies (left) and public compensation schemes (right) six to eight months after the flood. Number of firms that received or expect compensation are given on top.

² The Calamities Compensation Act (CCA) [*Wet Tegemoetkoming Schade bij Rampen*] is a compensation scheme from the Dutch government to partially compensate for otherwise uninsurable flood damages. Although flood damage from secondary water bodies is insurable in the Netherlands, the government still decided to partly compensate both homeowners and firms through the CCA.

³ The Disaster Fund accepted private donations and used that to partly compensate both residents and firms who experienced severe flood impacts.

3. Methodology

3.1. Estimation strategy

To estimate the impact of flooding on business interruption duration and revenue losses, two separate regressions have been applied using ordinary least squares (OLS). The regression equation for *business interruption* duration is as follows⁴:

$$\text{Business interruption}_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{inundation depth}_i + \beta_2 \text{still expected compensation}_i + \beta_k X'_i + a_i + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

Where business interruption in days for firm i is the function of the inundation depth at the ground floor of the property, the percentage of total direct damage compensation that is still expected, and additional control variables (Table 1). As flood impacts strongly differ between economic sectors (Koks et al., 2019), sector-fixed effects have been applied (a_i). The error term is given by ε_i .⁵ Previous studies that estimate empirical depth-damage functions for physical damage to properties have found non-linear relationships between inundation depth and physical flood damage (e.g. Wagenaar et al., 2017; Endendijk et al., 2023a). To identify the potential functional form for the regression, a flexible nonparametric model that does not impose a functional form has been applied (Anttila-Hughes & Hsiang, 2013). For this, inundation depths have been divided into bins as dummy variables and are included in a regression on business interruption in Appendix II. The outcomes of this flexible nonparametric regression model are visualized in Figure 9 in Appendix II. It stands out that inundation depth follows a linear relationship with business interruption, thus indicating that we can include inundation depth as a linear function in equation (1).

The regression equation for *revenue losses* is as follows:

$$\text{Revenue loss ratio}_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{business interruption}_i + \beta_2 \text{still expected compensation}_i + \beta_3 \text{access to firm}_i + \beta_4 \text{region dependency}_i + \beta_5 \text{business interruption}_i \times \text{region dependency}_i + \beta_k X'_i + a_i + \varepsilon_i \quad (2)$$

Where the revenue loss ratio for firm i is a function of business interruption duration, the firm's connection to the region, the number of days of the firm being difficult to reach after the flood, still expected insurance compensation, and other covariates. Flood events are very local events, but indirect impacts may reach far beyond the flood zone, where a disruption in local infrastructure and supply chains can occur (Merz et al., 2010). This implies that the impact of business interruption changes for firms with different connections to their region. To test for this difference, an interaction between business interruption and the region connection dummy has been introduced to the regression equation.

3.2. Propensity Score Matching (PSM)

A second goal of this study is to assess the impact of FDM measures taken on the firm level on business interruption duration. Endendijk et al. (2023a) show that estimating the effect of FDM measures using an OLS-regression biases outcomes, as individuals who perceive higher flood risk are more likely to implement FDM measures. A comparison between the group that has applied FDM measures and the group that has not will lead to an underestimation of the true effect, as these groups are different in their background characteristics prior to flooding.⁶ The same endogeneity problem is likely to occur with businesses. Using household survey data, Endendijk et al. (2023a) overcome this selection bias by

⁴ Controlling for the different waves of the distribution of the questionnaire did not influence results, and is thus excluded from the regression.

⁵ A Breusch-Pagan test identified heteroskedasticity in the data, for which robust standard errors have been applied (Woolridge, 2014).

⁶ For further explanation of this selection bias, see Endendijk et al. (2023a).

applying prior flood experience as an instrumental variable, a variable that is not available in our dataset. Hudson et al. (2014) and Sairam et al. (2019) overcome this selection bias through propensity score matching (PSM).

To identify the impact of FDM measures on business interruption duration, PSM has also been applied in this study. Each observation in the treatment group is matched with a control observation that is most similar based on their background characteristics that influence both flood damage and FDM uptake, such as hazard indicators, economic sector, and ownership of the firm's building. This matching process results in treatment and control groups that are similar in terms of expected flood risk, overcoming the problem of endogeneity (Rosenbaum & Rubin, 1985). First, a logistic regression will be applied to assign all observations a propensity score, which gives the predicted probability of an observation being in the control group based on all included confounding variables (Brookhart et al., 2006). Each treatment observation is matched with one or more control observations based on similar propensity scores, which allows for unbiased comparison between both groups.

There are three main assumptions when applying PSM. The first assumption is *unconfoundedness*, which means that all variables that could influence both the uptake of FDM measures and business interruption are included in the matching process (Caliendo & Kopeinig, 2008). The next assumption is *balancing*, which means that the treated and control groups should be balanced after matching so that both groups are comparable.⁷ The final assumption is *overlap*, which means that there should be sufficient overlap between the propensity score distributions of treatment and control. To make sure this assumption is satisfied, matching has been supplied with common support, where control observations are only matched if they lie within the upper and lower bound of the propensity scores of the treatment group (Caliendo & Kopeinig, 2008). Limitations of PSM are that the separate effect of all confounding variables cannot be estimated. For this reason, we apply PSM in addition to a regression in OLS. A second downside is that PSM may lead to loss of sample size and statistical power, due to larger uncertainty when estimating propensity scores (Austin, 2008).⁸

Finally, the outcomes of PSM can be sensitive to the choice of the matching algorithm (Caliendo & Kopeinig, 2008). To generate more robust results, we applied multiple matching methods: stratification matching, kernel matching, radius matching, and nearest-neighbor matching (Caliendo & Kopeinig, 2008). Nearest-neighbor matches control and treatment based on the most similar propensity score. Radius matching matches the treatment observation with all control observations within a specified bandwidth.⁹ Kernel matching matches a treatment observation with all observations in the control group, but gives a larger weight to the more similar propensity scores. Finally, stratification matching divides both groups into blocks. Each treatment observation within a block is compared with all control observations in the same block. A main disadvantage of stratification matching is that each block requires a sufficient number of observations, which makes estimates more uncertain compared to other matching methods when using small sample sizes (Li, 2013). For a more detailed description of the different matching methods, see Caliendo & Kopeinig (2008).

⁷ This assumption can be assessed by comparing the distribution of the control variables between the treatment and control groups. The balancing property has been satisfied for all applied matching methods (details not shown here).

⁸ To reduce uncertainty due to the matching process, we bootstrapped the standard errors.

⁹ A bandwidth of 0.05 is used in this study. Using smaller and larger bandwidths gives similar outcomes (details not shown here).

4. Results

4.1. Business interruption

The models in Table 2 explain the variation in business interruption duration between firms. Model 1 includes three variables that have similar significant effects throughout all other Models. It stands out that the coefficient for inundation depth is similar and significant throughout all models in Table 2, where 1 additional centimeter of inundation depth in the building is associated with 0.14-0.17 additional days of business interruption. This implies approximately four hours of additional business interruption. This effect can be explained due to the period it takes for the firm's property to dry and be cleaned (de Bruijn et al., 2015). Another variable that has a similar and significant coefficient throughout all models is the received compensation after the flood event. One additional percentage point of received damage compensation (compared to total expected compensation) six to eight months after the flood event is associated with 0.11-0.13 days fewer business interruption (three hours). Firms that experienced physical flood damage need time to repair these damages to start business again. The longer damage compensation has not been received, the more difficult it is for the firm to start reconstruction and resume business. The final included variable in Model 1 is the location dummy for a firm located near the Geul River, where the most economic damage has been observed (ENW, 2021). The Geul flows through a relatively small V-shaped valley with rapid response to upstream precipitation. For this reason, residents along the Geul River often had short warning times before the flood occurred, if they were warned at all (Endendijk et al., 2023b). The area along the Geul River faced the most disruption in local networks and destruction of infrastructure, which leads to longer business interruption, even if the firm itself did not face any water intrusion. This becomes apparent in Models 1-3, where firms located along the Geul River on average have five to seven days of additional business interruption compared to firms located in other areas. The Geul River dummy loses its significance and becomes smaller the more control variables are added to the model, which indicates that these newly added covariates explain some of the variation in business interruption duration previously captured by the dummy for the Geul River, which represents the area with the largest disruptions (ENW, 2021).

In Model 2, sector fixed effects are added to control for different interruption durations between economic sectors. The agricultural sector functions as the reference category for these sector dummies. The coefficients and significance of the variables are mostly similar compared to Model 1 and the fit of the model improves by adding sector-fixed effects. It stands out that the coefficients for the hospitality and health sectors are positive and significant. This implies that these sectors face longer business interruption compared to firms in the agricultural sector, which is also shown in Table 1. Model 3 includes additional hazard indicators. It is found that flow velocity and water contamination do not significantly impact business interruption. Compared to Model 2, Model 4 includes the firm's number of employees, the age of the building, and the period the firm can operate without stocks. None of these firm characteristics significantly impact business interruption after a flood event. Model 5 includes all covariates, which leads to similar results as found in the previous Models. Overall, the Models in Table 2 perform relatively well. Between 41.9% and 51.4% in the variation of business interruption duration has been explained.

It is also possible to distinguish an effect between firms that have been directly hit by the flood and firms that experience spillovers after the flood event due to the disruption of supply chains and infrastructure. The hazard indicators (inundation depth, flow velocity, and water contamination) as well as insurance compensation capture the effect of firms directly hit by the flood. Spillover effects are captured by the constant, the sector dummies, and the Geul River dummy, which corresponds to the firms in the most disrupted area. A robustness test in Table 5 in Appendix III¹⁰ confirms that the results on the hazard

¹⁰ A robustness test has been performed by running the same models as in Table 2 with only the directly flooded firms. It stands out that the coefficients of the hazard indicators do not differ compared to the same models in Table 2, as flood hazard indicators are uncorrelated with the other background variables included in the model. The significant relationship between inundation depth and business interruption remains, despite the small number of flooded firms included in the regression. Moreover, the fact that both flooded and non-flooded firms are included in the models in Table 2 does not affect the coefficients of the hazard indicators.

indicators (i.e., inundation depth, flow velocity, and contamination) are not affected by the fact that also non-flooded firms are included in the model.

Table 2

Fixed effects regression with business interruption in days as the dependent variable

VARIABLES	(1) Model 1	(2) Model 2	(3) Model 3	(4) Model 4	(5) Model 5
Inundation depth	0.168*** (0.026)	0.166*** (0.026)	0.138*** (0.029)	0.178*** (0.029)	0.148*** (0.032)
Received compensation (%)	-0.118** (0.054)	-0.129** (0.054)	-0.110** (0.050)	-0.133** (0.063)	-0.102* (0.061)
Flow velocity			1.247 (1.051)		1.345 (1.112)
Contamination			4.613* (2.673)		5.497* (3.185)
Employees				-0.009 (0.012)	-0.010 (0.014)
Building age				-0.014 (0.013)	-0.012 (0.014)
Supply dependency				-0.015 (0.041)	-0.011 (0.043)
Geul River	7.359*** (2.799)	5.471* (3.018)	5.113* (2.998)	4.400 (3.162)	3.983 (3.136)
<i>Sector</i>					
Service		-0.612 (2.233)	0.002 (2.746)	0.060 (2.228)	1.169 (2.763)
Manufacturing		4.427 (2.681)	7.022** (2.906)	3.698 (3.018)	6.784** (3.234)
Hospitality		7.128** (2.929)	8.501*** (3.198)	7.368** (3.646)	9.105** (3.992)
Retail		1.950 (2.411)	3.367 (2.773)	2.610 (2.454)	4.478 (2.925)
Public		0.692 (3.271)	2.056 (3.331)	0.637 (3.700)	2.277 (3.802)
Health		8.638* (5.028)	10.036* (5.358)	9.669* (5.533)	11.311* (5.876)
Constant	0.755 (0.831)	-2.164 (1.677)	-6.158** (3.048)	0.205 (2.523)	-4.521 (3.186)
Observations	177	177	170	153	147
Adjusted R-squared	0.419	0.459	0.473	0.498	0.514

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

4.2. Effect of adaptation measures on business interruption

PSM has been applied in Figure 5 to estimate the impact of FDM measures on business interruption. The matching process uses firm characteristics that drive FDM uptake. The treatment and control groups are matched on all the hazard characteristics from Table 1, as individuals who perceive higher flood severity, are more likely to adapt (Bubeck et al., 2012). The included exposure indicators are the firm's number of employees and the economic sector. Larger firms may have more financial capacity to adapt before a flood event and this adaptation possibilities may also differ between economic sectors (Li & Landry, 2018; Hudson et al., 2022). Finally, building age and ownership have been included in the matching process. Newer buildings may be more adapted in contrast to older buildings and firms who own their property can be more inclined to adapt to potential flooding (Dillenardt et al., 2022). As FDM uptake describes a physical damage process, the variables on firm accessibility and supply dependency have been excluded from the matching process. Another excluded variable from matching is insurance compensation, which takes place after FDM measures have already been applied. Moreover, Hudson et al. (2017) find no evidence of moral hazard with respect to insurance uptake and adaptation. Hence, this variable does not influence the uptake of these measures, making it an irrelevant confounding factor for PSM.

The coefficients of several FDM categories have been reported along with the 95%-confidence intervals in Figure 5. It seems like FDM measures have the potential to reduce business interruption up until two weeks, where mean business interruption was fifteen weeks for flooded firms, with some firms not being to operate for more than two months. Most coefficients range between two and four days of business interruption, where dry-proofing seems to be generally less effective compared to other categories, because they were often not high or strong enough. Structural FDM seems to be the most effective in reducing business interruption duration. Although these outcomes are not significant, it is likely that FDM reduces business interruption duration. To our knowledge, these are the only estimates in the literature that examine the relationship between FDM and business interruption, emphasizing the need for additional observational data.

A consequence of PSM is that the matching algorithm increases standard errors and that the number of observations in the treatment group is being reduced (Wilby & Keenan, 2012). For this reason, we cannot distinguish significant effects between FDM measures on business interruption. However, when applying multiple matching approaches for several FDM measure categories, we frequently observe a negative coefficient, although insignificant. The stratification method stands out, as it also gives some positive coefficient estimates, which may be a result of the sensitivity of this matching method to small sample sizes (Li, 2013). Positive coefficients are most frequently observed for dry-proofing and emergency measures, primarily due to the large share of placing sandbags in these categories. However, placing sandbags has often proven ineffective during this flood event, as they were either too low or not strong enough to protect the building from floodwater (Endendijk et al., 2023b). Consequently, these measures have often failed to reduce flood damage. Moreover, emergency FDM may be less suitable for PSM based on the aforementioned variables, as emergency FDM is mostly driven by early warnings, in contrast to the other FDM categories.

Figure 5

Coefficients and 95%-confidence intervals using Propensity Score Matching (PSM) to identify the effect of FDM measures on business interruption (days)¹¹.

¹¹ Matching has been applied using common support and with a maximum of five replacements. Standard errors are bootstrapped.

4.3. Revenue losses

Table 3 shows an OLS regression with the firm's revenue loss ratio as the dependent variable. This loss ratio relates revenue losses after the flood event to the firm's annual revenue of 2019. Model 1 only captures the relationship between business interruption and revenue losses. Model 2 adds received damage compensation, the number of days the firm was difficult to reach for customers, employees, or suppliers, and the Geul River dummy. One additional day of business interruption is associated with a 0.5 percentage point annual revenue loss, *ceteris paribus*. This significant effect slightly increases to 0.7 percentage points in Models 4 and 5.¹² The difficulty to access firms represents potential supply chain disruptions but does not significantly impact revenue losses. There is also no direct effect found of the effect of quick compensation on revenue losses, which means that there only is an indirect effect where quick insurance compensation reduces revenue losses through shorter business interruption duration (see Section 4.1).¹³ The Geul River dummy is not significant, which implies that revenue losses do not differ between the different flooded regions in Limburg, when controlling for business interruptions, insurance compensation and infrastructure disruption.

Model 3 adds the sector dummies, again with the agricultural sector as the reference category. It stands out that the service, manufacturing, retail, and health sectors all have significantly lower revenue losses compared to the agricultural sector, which is also shown in Table 1. This implies that the agricultural sector suffered one of the highest revenue losses, which can be explained due to the destruction of croplands. Low inundation depths can already cause harvests to fail, especially during summer (Förster et al., 2008). Most farms had their almost fully grown crops still on the field at the time of the flood. These farms lose the entire harvest of the flooded cropland, resulting in the loss of all potential sales from that property. These findings are supported by Figure 2, where the agricultural sector faced relatively short business interruption, but large revenue losses. We cannot distinguish a significant difference between the agricultural and the hospitality and public sectors, which implies that these sectors also faced large revenue losses. A reason for higher revenue losses in the hospitality sector may be that this sector is very location-bound. Restaurants and hotels do not open before their entire property is fully cleaned and repaired. In contrast, more footloose sectors, such as services and health, may start temporarily operating from non-affected properties, mitigating interruption and revenue losses. Tourism may have reduced as well, due to infrastructure disruption and potential safety issues (Rosselló et al., 2020). This way, the firms in the hospitality sector may have opened again, but fewer potential customers were in the area. Higher revenue losses in the public sector may be explained by the large fraction of sports associations included in this group. Sports accommodations may have been temporarily closed, which may have led to missed sponsorships income because of canceled games.

Model 4 adds a new variable that describes the firm's connection to the region and Model 5 also includes firm characteristics. The firm's connection to the region is expressed with a variable with the value 1 if more than 50% of the firm's customers or suppliers are located within a radius of 10 km around the firm. This variable is interacted with business interruption, to show how the impact of business interruption on revenue differs between firms based on the connection to their region. This effect has been visualized in Figure 6.

¹² Including the squared term of business interruption in the model to accommodate nonlinear effects did not yield a noteworthy correlation, suggesting that a linear model is satisfactory.

¹³ These direct and indirect effects have also been examined using a mediation regression, where the same results have been found (not reported in detail here).

Table 3*Regression revenue loss ratio (compared to revenue of 2019)*

VARIABLES	(1) Model 1	(2) Model 2	(3) Model 3	(4) Model 4	(5) Model 5
Business interruption	0.006*** (0.001)	0.005*** (0.002)	0.005*** (0.002)	0.007*** (0.002)	0.007*** (0.002)
Received compensation (%)		-0.000 (0.001)	-0.000 (0.001)	0.000 (0.001)	0.000 (0.001)
Access difficulty		0.006 (0.005)	0.004 (0.005)	0.008 (0.005)	0.007 (0.005)
Geul River		-0.008 (0.028)	0.036 (0.030)	0.015 (0.023)	0.023 (0.024)
Region connection				0.006 (0.020)	0.017 (0.023)
Business interruption × Region connection				-0.005*** (0.002)	-0.005** (0.002)
Supply dependency					0.001 (0.000)
Employees					0.000 (0.000)
<i>Sector</i>					
Service			-0.073** (0.033)	-0.070** (0.032)	-0.090** (0.038)
Manufacturing			-0.106*** (0.035)	-0.093*** (0.034)	-0.105*** (0.038)
Hospitality			-0.047 (0.042)	-0.053 (0.040)	-0.073* (0.040)
Retail			-0.097** (0.038)	-0.096*** (0.036)	-0.113*** (0.039)
Public			-0.044 (0.044)	-0.032 (0.040)	-0.061 (0.043)
Health			-0.187*** (0.056)	-0.181*** (0.053)	-0.202*** (0.056)
Constant	0.029*** (0.009)	0.016 (0.010)	0.078** (0.030)	0.070** (0.030)	0.062** (0.030)
Observations	148	148	148	148	133
Adjusted R-squared	0.349	0.367	0.448	0.524	0.494

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

The negative and significant coefficient implies that the impact of business interruption is larger for firms with less connection to the region compared to firms with a closer connection to the region. All firms experience higher revenue losses the longer business interruption lasts. However, firms that have less than 50% of their customers or suppliers within a 10 km radius face higher revenue losses compared to firms with a stronger connection to the region. This difference becomes larger the longer business interruption lasts. A potential explanation for this is that customers of firms with weak connection to their region are more likely to seek for alternatives during the firm being closed. These customers may prefer their new alternative or sign new contracts and will not return after the business has opened again,

leading to structurally lower revenues. The longer business interruption lasts, the more customers will look for alternatives. This may not be true for firms with a strong connection to the region. There may be no alternatives for customers close by. Alternatively, stronger local relationships with the firm make customers return after the business has opened again.

Figure 6

Marginal effect of business interruption on revenue losses for firms with low (light blue) and high (dark blue) connection to the region.

Note: Based on coefficients from Table 3

Figure 7 explores how this role of firm connection to the region differs per economic sector. Within economic sectors, firms with a weak connection to the region generally face higher revenue losses compared to firms with a stronger connection to the region. This is not the case for the manufacturing and retail sectors, where there are also few observations. The differences within the hospitality sector stand out, firms with a weak connection to the region on average face three times higher revenue losses compared to the group with a stronger connection. This supports the hypothesis of tourists temporarily staying away from the flooded area, resulting in lower demand. Firms in the hospitality sector that are less dependent on tourists may, therefore, experience lower revenue losses. Similar differences can be observed within the agricultural and health sectors. Firms with a strong connection to the region in the health sector may experience lower revenue losses during business interruption as patients are often connected to one dentist, pharmacy, or doctor in the region. Patients are, therefore, less likely to seek for alternatives, as they are used to a health care provider. In contrast, firms with weaker connections may face higher revenue losses as patients may opt for alternative healthcare providers in the absence of their usual facility. An alternative hypothesis for the agricultural, health and hospitality sector is that residents in the region support these businesses in the recovery process through additional demand or in-kind support.

Figure 7

Mean revenue loss ratio for firms with weak (light blue) and strong (dark blue) connection to their region, separated per economic sector. The number of observations is given on top of the boxes.

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5. Discussion

5.1. Comparison with previous literature

This study adds knowledge on business interruption duration, losses, and the potential impact of FDM measures following natural disasters. To our knowledge, only three studies investigated business interruption duration caused by flooding. Yang et al. (2016) assess the impact of pluvial flooding on business interruption and use a probabilistic approach to determine business interruption. The other studies that look into riverine flooding both use the same dataset from the 2013 Summer floods in Germany. Thielen et al. (2016) found a median business interruption of two weeks, which is higher compared to our findings in Figure 2. We find that more than 75% of firms within all economic sectors have resumed business after a bit more than a week. Sultana et al. (2018) seek a relationship between inundation depth and business interruption duration. Using Machine Learning, they identify business interruption to be mainly driven by hazard characteristics, such as inundation depth, duration, and water contamination. Similarly, in Table 2 it is observed that both inundation depth and water contamination are associated with longer business interruption. Sultana et al. (2018) used a bivariate linear regression to quantify the relationship between inundation depth and business interruption. Their model explains only 5% of the variation in business interruption duration, while our models, which include sector fixed effects and other covariates, explain 42%-51% of the variation.

We also examined the role of FDM on the building level in reducing business interruption duration for firms; a relationship which has, up to our knowledge, not been studied before. Moreover, empirical evidence on the effectiveness of FDM measures for reducing flood damage on the asset level is scarce, especially for commercial properties. Kuhlicke et al. (2020) use a regression to determine the damage-reducing potential of FDM measures for firms. They cannot disentangle a relationship between adaptation measures and flood impacts on firms. The most feasible explanation for this is, that firms who expect higher flood risk are more likely to take FDM measures, resulting in a positive selection bias (Endendijk et al., 2023a). Other studies on household FDM measures have applied an instrumental variable (IV)-regression (Endendijk et al., 2023a) or PSM (Hudson et al., 2014; Sairam et al., 2019) to overcome this selection bias. Sairam et al. (2019) and Hudson et al. (2014) both report the impact of FDM measures in absolute values, which makes their findings more difficult to compare with ours in terms of days. Endendijk et al. (2023a) find that FDM measures have the potential to reduce economic damage to buildings by 20-29%. Figure 5 shows that FDM reduces business interruption by 2-4 days, with a maximum of two weeks for most matching methods. Our FDM estimates should be interpreted with caution, as we were not able to identify significant effects due to the loss of statistical power from PSM and our relatively small sample size. However, these estimates indicate the potential of FDM measures in reducing business interruption duration, particularly for structural FDM measures.

Studies that estimate the impact of flooding on firms use several impact indicators, such as changes in capital, labor, productivity, profits, or value added. However, these studies often use a time scale longer than one year and cannot identify whether an individual firm was flooded or not (e.g. Leiter et al., 2009; Zhou & Botzen, 2021; Noth & Rehbein, 2019). Moreover, these studies are quite coarse in the determination of the flood extent, where a firm is classified as flooded when its city or region has been flooded. As a consequence, the average impact of flooding in existing studies includes both impacts on flooded firms as well as spillovers to other firms in the same region. We reduce the heterogeneity between different firm sizes by relating revenue losses to previous annual revenues, which indicates a stronger relationship between interruption and losses and improves the fit of the revenue loss model compared to Sultana et al. (2018). Our study is one of the first firm-level studies that can estimate the impact of flooding in a region, where the indirect impacts on flooded firms and spillover effects on non-flooded firms can be distinguished from each other. The relatively short timeframe of our study also explains the found negative effect of flooding on revenues, similar to what is found in other studies (e.g., Yang et al., 2016; Thielen et al., 2016; Wijayanti et al., 2017; Sultana et al., 2018). In the longer run, firm growth may be positive due to increased demand for goods and services for reconstruction in the

area, technological advancement because of the replacement of depreciated capital, or just macroeconomic growth in general (Zhou & Botzen, 2021).

5.2. Research implications

When interpreting our results, it should be noted that we report on the consequences of a relatively small flood event. For instance, the same flood event in the Ahr Valley in Germany or Hurricane Katrina in New Orleans caused much larger economic losses and disruptions (Fekete & Sandholz, 2021; Pistrika & Jonkman, 2010). As a consequence, infrastructure disruption and massive demand for reconstruction prolonged business interruption duration in these areas. We show an effect of inundation depth on business interruption duration, but one should be cautious when extrapolating this relationship to flood events of a much larger magnitude, where disruptions are larger. In this case, besides inundation depth, the total magnitude of economic losses caused by flooding should be considered.

Another limitation of our study is that it relies on self-reported revenue losses provided by the firms. While this approach is commonly used and offers valuable insights, it is important to acknowledge that self-reporting introduces the possibility of bias or inaccuracies in our data. Self-reported revenue losses are related to ‘business as usual’, so are an estimation of revenue losses rather than an accurate representation of impacts related to a counterfactual. However, this method helps mapping firm-level flood impacts, which gives more detailed flood characteristics and vulnerability indicators than modeled flood extents. Another limitation is that our study, which utilizes survey-based regression models, cannot fully examine interactions between economic sectors. Unlike approaches such as IO or CGE models, our models cannot capture complex interdependencies and feedback effects that can occur between economic sectors in the recovery process. We, therefore, stress that our findings are complementary to the findings from these macroeconomic models (e.g., Rose & Liao, 2005; Hallegatte, 2008; Koks et al., 2016), where especially our findings on business interruption duration may guide the use of recovery periods in IO and CGE models.

Current literature on IO and CGE models often makes strong assumptions about business interruption duration (Koks et al., 2016). In most cases, these models assume the recovery period after a flood event to last exactly one year, without any empirical calibration (Santos et al., 2014). The constant and significant coefficient of inundation depth in Table 2 calls for the inclusion of depth-duration functions in IO and CGE models. This allows for differentiation in recovery periods between different firms within a flooded region and provides more accuracy to these models, which is in contrast to the current approach in these macroeconomic models where different scenarios of business interruption duration are assumed for all firms within a flooded region. Moreover, our results show that a majority of flooded firms recover within two weeks (Table 1), where there are large outliers to longer business interruption durations.

As the outcomes of the impact on FDM measures taken on the firm level are quite uncertain, future studies can look more into this topic by collecting more observational data after flood events. Additionally, future studies that look into the impact of flooding on firm performance would benefit from the inclusion of connections between economic sectors. Some economic sectors are more closely connected to each other (Koks et al., 2016). This may indicate that disruptions in a closely connected economic sector will lead to larger revenue losses.

6. Conclusion

As the frequency and intensity of flood events are expected to increase under climate change, it is important to understand how flooding impacts businesses through interruption of business processes and revenue losses. Previous empirical studies on the impact of flooding on firms generally cannot distinguish separate direct effects on flooded firms and spillover effects to non-flooded firms. Moreover, flood magnitude and firm adaptation to flooding is often not considered in these existing studies. We, therefore, distributed a survey among firms in the flooded area after the 2021 Summer Floods in the Netherlands. Using a multivariate regression approach, flood characteristics have been found to explain business interruption duration, which resulted in depth-duration functions. These functions serve the purpose of reducing reliance on assumptions regarding business interruption duration and enabling a more nuanced distinction in the level of business interruption experienced across varying degrees of flood impacts in models that capture indirect impacts on firms. The role of flood damage mitigation (FDM) measures taken on the building level on business interruption has been identified using Propensity Score Matching (PSM). This approach overcomes the problem of endogeneity, which is caused by firms that expect higher flood damage being more likely to adopt these measures.

It is found that one additional centimeter of inundation depth is associated with four hours of additional business interruption, where one day of business interruption costs a firm on average 0.5% of its annual revenue. Our findings indicate that FDM measures on the building level have the potential to reduce business interruption with a maximum of two weeks and an average of three to four days. However, these findings should be interpreted with caution, as it was not possible to identify significant effects of FDM due to a small sample size. Firm FDM uptake is relatively low compared to households. Therefore, encouraging and supporting businesses in implementing FDM measures can help mitigate the negative impacts of business interruption. Governments can actively provide flood risk information to firms and insurers can incentivize FDM uptake by using premium discounts. Another way to support firm resilience is by strengthening local networks and customer loyalty. Firms that are more closely connected to their region, face less adverse effects from business interruption compared to firms less connected to the region. This difference is likely to be caused by customers returning to firms with a stronger connection to the region, where customers of other firms are more likely to seek for substitutes. Next, commercial flood insurance uptake is relatively low in the Netherlands. However, it is found that quick loss compensation indirectly reduces revenue losses by shortening the duration of business interruption, calling for higher insurance uptake and efficient and streamlined insurance and government damage compensation. A way to accomplish this is by stimulating insurance uptake and establishing a central point for households and firms to claim their flood damage compensation, which can be distributed among different insurers at a later stage.

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Appendix

Appendix I: Geographical distribution of business interruption

Figure 8

Average business interruption per postal code area (N=129)¹⁴

¹⁴ Due to the privacy regulations in the Netherlands, the location of some firms is unknown, as respondents were given the option to withhold their addresses.

Appendix II: Flexible nonparametric model of inundation depth on business interruption

Table 4

Flexible nonparametric regression model for business interruption and inundation depth divided into bins

VARIABLES	(1) Model 1
Inundation depth (1-20cm)	2.027 (3.152)
Inundation depth (21-50 cm)	6.133 (4.082)
Inundation depth (51-100 cm)	18.689*** (3.577)
Inundation depth (101-200 cm)	26.722** (7.956)
Inundation depth (201-400 cm)	42.206*** (2.102)
Constant	2.697 (1.645)
Observations	177
Number of sectors	8
Adjusted R-squared	0.345

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Figure 9

Visualization of the nonparametric regression model

Appendix II: Robustness test with only flooded firms

Table 5

Fixed effects regression with business interruption in days as the dependent variable with only flooded firms

VARIABLES	(1) Model 1	(2) Model 2	(3) Model 3	(4) Model 4	(5) Model 5
Inundation depth	0.169*** (0.031)	0.169*** (0.031)	0.136*** (0.037)	0.178*** (0.037)	0.151*** (0.043)
Received compensation (%)	-0.134* (0.070)	-0.145** (0.067)	-0.129** (0.063)	-0.137* (0.074)	-0.111 (0.073)
Flow velocity			1.777 (2.710)		1.435 (3.761)
Contamination			6.044 (3.777)		6.520 (5.048)
Employees				-0.019 (0.028)	-0.022 (0.041)
Building age				-0.028 (0.025)	-0.020 (0.028)
Supply dependency				-0.010 (0.094)	-0.000 (0.096)
Geul River	11.217** (4.467)	9.647* (5.006)	9.098* (4.941)	7.470 (5.496)	6.969 (5.530)
<i>Sector</i>					
Service		-1.980 (5.625)	0.392 (6.535)	2.978 (6.518)	5.388 (7.569)
Manufacturing		11.577 (7.202)	15.405** (7.443)	13.719 (8.572)	18.040* (9.265)
Hospitality		14.941*** (5.230)	17.008*** (5.536)	18.897*** (6.866)	20.675*** (7.179)
Retail		-0.974 (6.120)	-0.068 (6.779)	5.714 (6.314)	6.147 (7.700)
Public		2.848 (4.719)	5.357 (5.222)	2.907 (6.154)	5.647 (6.844)
Health		17.336** (7.843)	18.772** (7.974)	21.338** (9.762)	22.713** (9.774)
Constant	12.612* (6.948)	5.768 (5.870)	-2.399 (7.440)	6.701 (7.704)	-3.198 (9.592)
Observations	83	83	83	66	66
Adjusted R-squared	0.348	0.464	0.484	0.486	0.502

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1